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**THE IMAGE OF GERMANY IN THE CONTEXT
OF MUTUAL RELATIONS BETWEEN THE UKRAINIANS AND
THE GERMANS, AS IT IS PRESENTED IN INTELLECTUAL
HERITAGE OF HISTORIAN AND GEOGRAPHER
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Predominantly, national state trend in Ukrainian historical thought was mainly formed in Austrian-ruled Galicia. In the Austro-Hungarian monarchy, where social relations were characterized by a far greater degree of democracy than in tsarist Russia, Ukrainian national problem had some chances for a successful solution. It could not but result in the development of certain interpretations and academic approaches to the analysis of national question in Galicia by Ukrainian intellectuals. In this context they offered their vision of nations, which were politically and culturally dominant over Ukrainians – the Russians, the Poles, and, indeed, the Germans. The following figures should be mentioned, in the first place, as distinguished representatives of national state trend in Ukrainian historical thought: a historian and geographer Stepan Rudnytskyi (1877–1937), a historian and sociologist Olherd Bochkovskyi (1885–1939), a law historian, lawyer and sociologist Volodymyr Starosolskyi (1878–1942) and others¹.

¹ In their vision of the Ukrainian nation right for self-determination within their own ethnic territory these scholars focused extensively on the role of Germany and the German people in attainment by the Ukrainian people of their own republican-democratic state as the basis of the Ukrainian nation, defined the national idea and national psychology relying, for the most part, upon corresponding ideas of leading German scholars. For more details on the concepts of these scholars, see: В. ПОТУЛЬНИЦЬКИЙ, *Нариси з української політології (1819–1991): Навчальний посібник*, К., 1994, с. 226–300; В. ПОТУЛЬНИЦЬКИЙ, ‘Політична доктрина Володимира Старосольського’ [Political doctrine of Volodymyr Starosolskyi] [in:] *Almanakh “Молода нація”* [Almanac “Young Nation”], vol. 9 (К., 1998) 30–44; ГВІДО ГАУСМАНН, ‘Територія України: Внесок Степана Рудницького в історію просто-рово-територіального мислення в Україні’ [The territory of Ukraine: the contribution

In his papers academician Rudnytskyi traces the historical ties that developed between the Ukrainians and the Germans, and stresses that these links were constructive and developed in the Middle Ages, as well as in the nineteenth and in the twentieth centuries. In the medieval era German cultural influences could penetrate to Ukraine exclusively through Poland; in particular, ‘intense German colonization in Poland led to excellent development of cities and urban life, high level of culture, craft and trade’². Therefore, German neighbourhood, in his view, had only beneficial influences on medieval Poland and Ukraine. In the nineteenth century the Ukrainians owed to official German nationalism the rise of Ukrainian nationalism that occurred under its influence, which ‘in some of its specific forms, ornaments and wreaths is truly the product of the nineteenth century, and, likewise, the product of capitalism, feudalism, militarism, etc.’³ In the twentieth century the fates of Germany and Ukraine intertwined so tightly that both the Central Council and the Hetman State in 1918 were established with German. The fall of monarchy and revolutions in Germany and Austria naturally resulted in the collapse of the Hetman State, which failed being left without such a mighty ally as the German Empire. ‘Threatened by the Red Army’ – the scholar comments upon this matter – ‘the Central Council concluded peace in Brest with Germany and Austria in order to gain power in Ukraine with their assistance ... The fall of Germany and Austria in November 1918 led to the fall of new Hetmanate which was substituted by Directory’⁴. This alliance, which brought the rise of the Hetman State to Ukrainian lands, in Rudnytskyi’s opinion, was nothing but a mutual compromise on both sides. In recognizing Ukraine as an independent state and by concluding peace in Brest, the Germans were guided by careful thought. Explaining the core of these mutual settlements, Rudnytskyi states: ‘Germany had an army, though had no bread; Ukraine

of Stepan Rudnytskyi to the history of spatial and territorial thinking in Ukraine] [in:] АНДРЕАС КАШПЕЛЕР (eds.), *Україна. Процеси націотворення [Ukraine. The processes of nation building]*, К., 2011, с. 154–167; G. HAUSMANN, ‘Maps of the Borderlands: Russia and Ukraine’ [in:] ROISIN HEALY and ENRICO DAL LAGO (eds.), *The Shadow of Colonialism on Europe’s Modern Past*, London, 2014, p. 194–210.

² СТЕПАН РУДНИЦЬКИЙ, *Українська справа зі становища політичної географії [The Ukrainian matter in the state of political geography]*, Берлін, 1923, с. 38, 43.

³ СТЕПАН РУДНИЦЬКИЙ, *До основ українського націоналізму [Towards the foundation of the Ukrainian nationalism]*, Відень; Прага, 1923, с. 28.

⁴ СТЕПАН РУДНИЦЬКИЙ, *Чому ми хочемо самостійної України [Why do we want independent Ukraine]*, Л., 1994, с. 357–358.

had enough bread, though was left without army; Muscovia had none of these. The situation was of such kind then. Ukrainian revolutionary government, simultaneously threatened by Russia and Germany, chose the better of two evils – peace with Germany and its help against Russia⁵.

Introducing the example of German agriculture as instructive for Ukrainian peasantry, the scholar notes that in Germany a farmer manages to harvest three or four times more crops from one acre of land than in Russia, Poland or Ukraine, with the caveat that ‘land fertility in Germany is far less than in Ukraine’⁶. Likewise, it applies to cattle breeding, mining, industry and trade, water and land ways, railways, post, and telegraph. According to the historian, such examples should be provided to oppose the supporters of Moscow culture in Ukraine. ‘All those Ukrainians’ – he states – ‘who idly talk about ‘high’ Moscow culture, should invest some effort into comparing the achievements of the Russian culture in exceptionally rich Ukraine or Siberia with those, for example, of the German culture against the background of poor nature in Germany!’⁷

In addition to lasting historical ties, which laid the foundation for friendly relations between the two nations, it is Germany, as regarded by Rudnytskyi, that has to serve as a model for the Ukrainians both in managing the household and in establishing strong political and military power, as well as in developing the capital city as an efficient state cultural centre. Premised on the requirements of political and economic geography, Rudnytskyi attaches great importance in nation building to the capital of Ukraine, which should be situated where the core of state political life is located, which is intended to tie in the knot of international controversies. As the above-mentioned function of core and knot has traditionally been ignored giving place to leader’s whim or decisive role of public in appointing the capital of Ukraine, in order not to repeat past mistakes in the future the Ukrainians should be guided by the example of Germany. ‘A good example in the direction (choice of the capital – *V. P.*)’ – the scholar notes – ‘is provided by Germany. Throughout the Middle Ages and up to 1870 it had no capital. In theory, initially Aachen was the capital, followed by Rome; the first one was situated in a bizarre location, whereas the second one was far beyond Germany. Frankfurt was exclusively a coronation town. Over the period from the thirteenth to the fifteenth centuries Habs-

⁵ СТЕПАН РУДНИЦЬКИЙ, *Українська справа...*, с. 178.

⁶ СТЕПАН РУДНИЦЬКИЙ, *Чому ми хочемо самостійної України*, с. 73.

⁷ *Ibid.*

burg rulers permanently resided in Vienna, similarly located beyond the German lands, away from the core region of Ukraine'. As a consequence, this state of affairs had, the historian continues, '... a very bad effect on the development of 'The Holy Roman Empire of the German Nation'. It was Prussian hegemony in 1871 that gave Germany its first distinct capital of Berlin'⁸. It is Rudnytskyi's firm belief that, following the lead of Germany, it is crucial to set 'the capital of united Ukraine at such a place to which the centre of balance of the whole Southern and Eastern Europe would relocate all by itself'⁹.

Being convinced that the fundamental concepts of every nation are territory and race, which constitute a ground for consequent national characteristics: historical and political traditions and competition, language and culture¹⁰, and being the follower of racial theory of Ukrainian nationalism, Rudnytskyi assigns to the Germans, like other 'distinctive', in terms of race, people, a special place in keeping Ukrainian nation from extinction or absorption by 'second rate' nations¹¹. 'In this matter', – Rudnytskyi states, – 'it is advantageous that the Ukrainian element is combined with the so-called northern race (the Scandinavians, most of the Anglo-Saxons, and the Germans), as well as with the Southern Slavs and the Czechs who are racially related to us. Instead, the combinations with the Poles, the Muscovites, the Romanians, the Turks and the Tartars, the Jews, etc. are not beneficial'¹². Reporting that the milieu of the Ukrainian intelligentsia, by contrast, is dominated by marriages with the representatives of Russian, Polish or Jewish people, which generally lead to overall family Russification or Polonization, the scholar generally views such mixed marriages as being a destructive factor for cultivating true and distinctive Ukrainian national spiritual culture. 'Intermarriage combinations with more worthy, in terms of race, peoples (the Scandinavians, the Anglo-Saxons, the Germans, the other Slavs of the Aryan race)' – he states – 'are very infrequent among our intellectuals. It is regrettable, as their benefits would be great!'¹³

⁸ Not only did Berlin take over the concentration of "Prussian spirit" as the core for formation of German imperial militarism, but it also had a remarkably favorable geographical location in terms of political and economic geography. See: *Ibid.*, c. 362–363.

⁹ *Ibid.*, c. 368.

¹⁰ СТЕПАН РУДНИЦЬКИЙ, *До основ українського націоналізму*, с. 81.

¹¹ СТЕПАН РУДНИЦЬКИЙ, *Чому ми хочемо самостійної України*, с. 74.

¹² СТЕПАН РУДНИЦЬКИЙ, *До основ українського націоналізму*, с. 61–62.

¹³ *Ibid.*, c. 79. It should be noted that at the beginning of the twentieth century Western European anthropological science established the approach of distinguishing nations with clear

Rudnytskyi supports his suggestions as to reliance of Ukrainian daily activities upon the German models of organizing society, industry, science, literature, art, commerce, etc. with arguments on benefits the German people could obtain by maintaining friendly relations with the Ukrainian people and by providing assistance in building their state. Thereby, he offers and justifies two central ideas: 1) gain from the formation of the Ukrainian state as a future political agent capable of preventing the escalation of new European conflicts; 2) gain from the geographical position of Ukraine at the crossroads, as a territory, which could potentially contribute to achievement and fulfilment of Germany's geopolitical goals.

Furthermore, Rudnytskyi presumes that the negative result in forming the Ukrainian state could turn a new order in Eastern Europe into a challenging issue and cause severe interstate conflicts in the near future. This issue should be settled exclusively by establishing the Ukrainian national state within its ethnographic borders, as the national territory should be considered 'irrevocable holiness'¹⁴. This national territory, where the Ukrainian people live, must be indivisible and delineate the Ukrainian state within its ethnic borders. 'The formation of the Ukrainian national state within its ethnographic borders is a single way of preventing unrests and conflicts in the southeast corner of Europe, which is so important for world economy and world politics. Without the national Ukrainian state, we shall soon face new grave revolutionary and war disasters'¹⁵.

It seems crucial to follow why Rudnytskyi believes that Ukraine is destined to prevent future conflicts and what role is assigned to Western Europe in avoiding them. In order to sustain his assumptions, the scholar advances a number of reasons. Initially, it is the fact that from the fifteenth to the eighteenth century Ukraine was located at the crossroads of three worlds: the Western, the Oriental-Islamic and nomadic Asian one. The combinations of these three influences culminated in such a situation when none of them surpassed the others in the development of Ukrainian national character and affected it in a dominant manner. Therefore, in the

racial type (gruppen, die einen reinen Rassentypus aufweisen), on the one hand, and nations presenting distinct anthropological hybrid (eine deutliche antropologische Mischung), on the other hand. See: FRANZ BOAS, *Kultur und Rasse*, Leipzig, 1914; OTTO RECHE, *Rasse und Sprache. Sonderabdruck aus dem Archiv für Anthropologie*, N. F. Bd. XVIII, S. 208–218.

¹⁴ СТЕПАН РУДНИЦЬКИЙ, *Огляд національної території України [Review of national territory of Ukraine]*, Берлін, 1923, с. 9.

¹⁵ СТЕПАН РУДНИЦЬКИЙ, *Українська справа...*, с. 117.

matter of state building the Ukrainian people are marked by such a feature as ‘remarkable primitivism – savagery’¹⁶. Monarchism, feudalism, bureaucracy, militarism, parliamentarism in ‘bourgeois’ sense, etc. are all alien to Ukrainian historical and political traditions’, as ‘...the Ukrainians are typical agrarian and peasant people’¹⁷. The above-mentioned distinctive feature of Ukrainian historical path and the rise of national state within ethnographic borders make that particular symbiosis that Europe lacks in order to resolve conflicts in the manner different from how it has previously been done with the participation of Ukraine keeping in mind its specific nature.

Additionally, Rudnytskyi is convinced that distinguished and unique geographical position of Ukraine could best contribute to the achievement and implementation of Germany’s far-reaching geopolitical plans¹⁸. By linking this assertion with his own idea of building the national Ukrainian state within its ethnographic borders, Rudnytsky notes that ‘... the Ukrainian state within its ethnographic borders shall entirely divide Russia from its old spheres of influence in Asia Minor. Indeed, even the formation of the Eastern European States Federation with or without Muscovia does not seem advantageous for the German expansion policy and postpones the possibility of expansion cooperation for distant future’. Instead, ‘... the southeast corner of Europe – Ukraine, will remain neutral for a long time similar to the western corner – Spain. Thus, Germany, together with other Western states, will derive benefit from this neutrality’¹⁹. Given the fact that Ukraine, on the one hand, owing to its geographical position dominates over the access from Eastern Europe and the Balkan States to Armenia, Persia, Mesopotamia,

¹⁶ The point is that “Western political and state forms, that were developed in the Middle Ages, redesigned by new age and are currently destroyed in the most recent time period, failed to get deeply rooted in Ukraine”. See: СТЕПАН РУДНИЦЬКИЙ, *До основ українського націоналізму*, с. 101–102.

¹⁷ *Ibid.*, с. 102.

¹⁸ In this context, according to the researcher, one should take into account a number of circumstances of the historical development of Germany in the most recent time period. The first is the fact that Germany was somewhat late in joining the division of the world and gaining overseas colonies, while the rapid development of industry and trade along with increasing population forced Germany to deploy expansionist policy. Secondly, at the time of Wilhelm II Germany embarked on this expansion in the South East, Turkish Asia, Egypt and Sudan, intending to establish a great colonial power with Baghdad Railway being its geographic symbol. Thirdly, according to the expert in geopolitics, amazing endurance of the German people will never leave expansionist aspirations towards the South East. See: СТЕПАН РУДНИЦЬКИЙ, *Українська справа...*, с. 181–185.

¹⁹ *Ibid.*, с. 190–191.

etc., that is to the states which are important for political expansion of Germany, and, on the other hand, is located on the shortest land route from Western Europe to India with its middle segment running two thousand kilometres along Ukraine, Rudnytskyi is convinced that the fate of Germany depends on how future political situation in Ukraine will evolve²⁰.

Rudnytskyi believes that it is ultimately in the best interests of Germany to contribute to the task of 'politically organizing the Ukrainian peasantry and building a large durable peasant (Ukrainian national – *V. P.*) state on this foundation'²¹. It stands to mention, that he deems it possible through the recognition Europeans of the fact that Ukrainian vernacular culture is akin to German, as it is purely Aryan and could possibly 'throw its beneficial shade up to the shores of the Indian and the Pacific Oceans'; moreover, it is based on such attributes kindred to the Germans as 'purity of race, eugenics, the cult of individualism, humanism, the best autonomous and federal premises, freedom of thought, aristocracy of spirit and democracy of matter – major features of new Ukrainian national culture'²².

Conclusions

The historical ties that had developed between the Ukrainians and the Germans, academician Rudnytskyi, being supporter of building Ukrainian national state in its ethnic borders on the basis of nationalism, emphasized that these ties were exceptionally constructive for Ukraine in their nature. He believed that Ukraine had notably benefited from the German neighbourhood, as Ukrainian nationalism rose in the late nineteenth – early twentieth century in Galicia influenced by German nationalism, whereas the Central Council and the Hetman State were formed in 1918 on the ruins of the Russian Empire owing to German military presence.

Rudnytskyi believed that the Germans should serve as a model for the Ukrainians in the issues of farming, industry and trade, high level of science and culture, as well as in choosing the capital as a centre of political life and international relations. Additionally, he interpreted the Germans from the perspective of racial theory and considered the Ukrainian people to be akin to the Germans. Hence, he preferred marriages of the Ukrainians with the Germans, the Anglo-Saxons and the Scandinavians

²⁰ СТЕПАН РУДНИЦЬКИЙ, *Українська справа.*, с. 50–51. Also see: СТЕПАН РУДНИЦЬКИЙ, *Чому ми хочемо самостійної України*, с. 81.

²¹ СТЕПАН РУДНИЦЬКИЙ, *До основ українського націоналізму*, с. 111.

²² *Ibid.*, с. 161–162.

and opposed marriages with the Poles, the Russians, the Romanians, the Tatars and the Jews, most of which leads, in his opinion, to family Russification or Polonization.

In his ambition to build a national Ukrainian state in its ethnic borders, Rudnytskyi relied, first and foremost, upon Germany. In justifying the necessity of a such Germany-centered orientation for national Ukrainian state, he demonstrated a pragmatic approach, strengthening his arguments with considerations on benefits Germany and the German people could gain from close ties with Ukraine. These gains, according to Rudnytskyi's vision, included, on the one hand, the advantages the Germans could obtain from existence of future Ukrainian state as a factor capable of preventing the escalation of European conflicts, and, on the other hand, from the geographical position of Ukraine at the crossroads, which could contribute to achieving Germany's geopolitical goals.

It is remarkable, that Rudnytskyi believed that Ukraine could never form a nation if it followed the mechanical model nation-building, alien to its nature, in accordance with which states were formed in England, France, Spain, and Russia. On the contrary, it is an organic way paved by Germany, where the formed nation builds a state, that is natural for Ukraine. If Ukraine builds its own state on a solid modern national ground, it has, in the opinion of Rudnytskyi, to be formed being in organic connection with the German world as two parts of one whole.

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Бачення Німеччини в контексті взаємовідносин між німцями та українцями в інтелектуальній спадщині історика та географа Степана Рудницького.

Анотація. Автор статті, використовуючи архівні документи та літературу, відтворює концептуальні погляди на спільні сторінки німецько-української історії, викладені у працях видатного українського вченого, академіка Степана Рудницького. У статті доведено, що Рудницький надавав величезного значення німецьким впливам на постання українського націєтворення і підкреслював, що ці зв'язки носили для України лише конструктивний характер. Вчений вважав, що німецьке сусідство мало для України тільки корисні наслідки, оскільки навіть український націоналізм постав наприкінці XIX – на

початку ХХ століття в Галичині під впливом німецького націоналізму, а Центральна Рада та Гетьманська держава у 1918 р. змогли утворитися на руїнах Російської імперії завдяки німецькій військовій присутності.

Автор встановлює, що Рудницький був переконаний у своєму твердженні, що німці мають служити для українців зразком у справі ведення господарства, промисловості і торгівлі, досягнення високого рівня науки і культури та навіть вибору столиці, як центру політичного життя держави і міжнародних зв'язків. Вчений, як і багато його сучасників – науковців у Німеччині, Австрії та Україні, трактував німців з перспективи расистської теорії і вважав українців спорідненим німцям народом.

Автор відтворює думки Рудницького на питання етноцентризму, показавши на основі джерел, що науковець, у своєму прагненні побудови національної української держави в її етнічних кордонах, орієнтувався насамперед і майже виключно на Німеччину. Обґрунтовуючи для національно-державницької України необхідність саме такої, німецькоцентричної орієнтації, Рудницький демонстрував прагматичний підхід, підкріплюючи свої аргументи міркуваннями щодо зиску, який матиме від стосунків з Україною сама Німеччина і німецький народ. Цей зиск, у відповідності з баченням академіка, залежав, з одного боку, від корисності для німців факту існування майбутньої української держави, як чинника, спроможного запобігти ескалації європейських конфліктів, а, з іншого боку, від географічного положення України на перетині шляхів, яке спроможне посприяти досягненням геополітичних цілей Німеччини. Якщо Україна, підкреслював вчений, будуватиме власну державу на модерному національному ґрунті, вона, на його переконання, має формуватися, перебуваючи в органічному зв'язку з німецьким світом, як дві частини одного цілого.

Ключові слова. Україна, Німеччина, німецько-українські відносини, Степан Рудницький.